

Predictive Accuracy of Intraocular Lens Power Calculation by Immersion A- Scan Biometry and Contact A- Scan Biometry: A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Background: A-scan ultrasound biometry (A-scan biometry/ A-scan) is mainly used to determine the axial length of the eye with the help of an ultrasound device. Axial length of eye is an important parameter to calculate Intraocular lens (IOL) power prior to cataract surgery. Different formulae to calculate the IOL power need axial length value along with keratometry value (calculated using a keratometer). Sometimes, the corneal compression caused during the A-scan measurement gives wrong values of the axial length. The objective of the present study was to compare accuracy of intraocular lens power calculation by immersion A-scan biometry and contact A-scan biometry in a tertiary care centre.

Material and Methods: The present hospital based comparative observational study was conducted at Department of Ophthalmology from July 2024 to September 2024. A total of 100 consecutive patients who underwent phacoemulsification and IOL implantation were included in the study. Informed written consent was taken from the participants of the study. Patients were divided into Group A as immersion group and Group B as Contact A-scan group with 50 patients each. Data entry and data analysis was done using MS Excel and epi info version 7.

Results: Most of the patients were females in Group A (70%) and Group B (62%) with no statistically significant difference ($P > 0.05$). The mean axial length in group A and Group B was 23.07 and 22.65 with statistically significant difference ($P < 0.05$). The mean IOL power in group A and Group B was 20.37 and 21.21 respectively with statistically significant difference ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The present study concludes that the immersion technique had better repeatability compared to Contact A-scan for intraocular lens power calculation.

Keywords: Intraocular Lens Power, Immersion A- Scan, Contact A- Scan.

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Introduction

In routine ophthalmological practice, ocular biometric measurements are made, including axial length, anterior chamber depth, and lens thickness. The pre-operative assessment of cataract surgery is where this is primarily indicated. Even in cases where no intraocular lens (IOL) is implanted, modern cataract surgery is regarded as a type of refractive surgery that aims to give exceptional vision in terms of refractive correction in addition to restoring visual clarity.

Standardization of methods is necessary to guarantee precise measurements, which are crucial for accurately calculating the necessary IOL power for cataract surgery. This is a crucial step in ocular biometry to achieve the intended post-operative refractive outcome.[1,2] In order to achieve the intended refractive results following cataract and

refractive surgery, it is crucial to accurately calculate the intraocular lens (IOL) power.[3] The conventional method for determining lens thickness, axial length, and anterior chamber depth is A-scan ultrasonography. A trace of ocular spikes from the cornea to the orbital fat is shown on the monitor when an ultrasonic beam is passed into the eye using a transducer and returns after striking intraocular structures. [4]

Biometry values can be acquired by optical, touch, or immersion techniques. With the widely used contact/applanation approach, an ultrasonic probe is placed on the central cornea, gently indenting the surface and causing varying degrees of corneal compressions that could introduce mistakes into the values. [5] The immersion A-scan biometry is largely observer independent and employs a saline-

filled scleral (Prager) shell between the probe and the eye. [6,7] Due to refractive surprises from improper intraocular lens power and inconsistent axial length readings acquired, it was necessary to repeat biometric measures frequently and have a second operator do so.

Hence, the present study was conducted to compare accuracy of intra-ocular lens power calculation by immersion A-scan biometry and contact A-scan biometry in a tertiary care centre.

Objective: To compare accuracy of intra-ocular lens power calculation by immersion A-scan biometry and contact A-scan biometry in a tertiary care centre.

Material and Methods:

The present hospital based comparative observational study was conducted at the Department of Ophthalmology from July 2024 to September 2024. A total of 100 consecutive patients who underwent phacoemulsification and IOL implantation were included in the study. Patients not giving a valid consent, with presence of any corneal pathology, ocular developmental anomaly, ocular

tumours and non-consenting individuals were excluded from the study. Permission from the Ethical Committee was taken prior to commencement of the study and informed written consent was taken from the participants of the study. Patients were divided into Group A as Immersion group and Group B as Contact A-scan group with 50 patients each. The Demographic and medical details of the patients were recorded in the proforma sheet along with the symptoms preceding the disease. The ophthalmic examination was done by a single ophthalmologist. Best corrected visual acuity for distance and near were recorded.

Measurements were taken using immersion A-scan biometry first followed by the contact A-scan biometry by the same examiner and using the same machines. The Slit lamp examination of the anterior and posterior segments was performed prior to surgery. All the recent investigations done from the same institute were also noted down in the questionnaire. Data entry and data analysis was done using MS Excel and epi info version 7 (available from WHO).

Results:

Table 1: Comparison of demographic characteristics among two groups: (n=100)

Variables		Group A (n=50) (%)	Group B (n=50) (%)	P value*
Age group (years)	41– 50	4 (8.0%)	2 (4.0%)	X ² =5.39 P<0.001
	51– 60	24(48.0%)	7 (14.0%)	
	61– 70	17(34.0%)	18(36.0%)	
	71– 80	5 (10.0%)	17(34.0%)	
	81 -90	0 (0.0%)	6 (12.0%)	
Gender	Female	35(70.0%)	31(62.0%)	X ² =1.43 P=0.398
	Male	15(30.0%)	19(38.0%)	

(*P value <0.05 statistically significant by Chi square test)

The majority of patients in group A was from age group 51-60 years (48%) compared to group B which were from age group 61-70 years (36%) with statistically significant difference (P<0.05). The most of patients were females in Group A (70%) and Group B (62%) with no statistically significant difference (P>0.05). (Table 1)

Table 2: Comparison of Biometric characteristics among two groups: (n=100)

Variables		Group A	Group B	P value
Post OP Refraction (D)	Mean	-0.63	-1.09	<0.001 (Significant)
	Std. Deviation	0.18	0.45	
Axial Length (mm)	Mean	23.07	22.65	0.008 (Significant)
	Std. Deviation	1.13	1.04	
IOL	Mean	20.37	21.21	0.031 (Significant)
	Std. Deviation	2.81	2.65	

The mean post-operative refraction in group A and Group B were -0.63 and -1.09 respectively with statistically significant difference (P<0.05). The mean axial lengths in group A and Group B were 23.07 and 22.65 with statistically significant

difference (P<0.05). The mean IOL powers in group A and Group B was 20.37 and 21.21 with statistically significant difference (P<0.05). (Table 2)

Table 3: Comparison of Post-operative visual acuity among the two groups: (n=100)

BCVA	Post-Operative		P value
	Group A	Group B	
< 6/12	1 (2.0%)	42 (84.0%)	<0.001
> 6/12	49 (98.0%)	8 (16.0%)	
Total	50 (100.0%)	50 (100.0%)	

The majority of patients in group A had BCVA >6/12 (98%) compared to group B (84%) with statistically significant difference ($P<0.05$). (Table 3).

Discussion

The most common procedure performed in ophthalmology, cataract surgery, relies heavily on ocular biometry. Accurately calculating the intra-ocular lens (IOL) power implanted during surgery depends on precise measurement of ocular biometry variables, particularly axial length measurement. The present study was conducted to compare the accuracy of intra-ocular lens power calculation by immersion A-scan biometry and contact A-scan biometry in a tertiary care centre.

In the present study, the majority of patients in Immersion A-scan group was younger compared to Contact A-scan group with statistically significant difference ($P<0.05$). Most of the patients were females in Immersion A-scan group and Contact A-scan group with no statistically significant difference ($P>0.05$). (Table 1) Ademola-Popoola DS et al.[8] in a study observed ages ranged from 18 to 95 years with a mean of 64.7 (SD \pm 12.9) years. There were 55 (59.8%) males and 37 (40.2%) females, with a male to female ratio of 1.5:1.

In the present study, the mean post-operative refractions in Immersion A-scan group and Contact A-scan group were -0.63 and -1.09 respectively with statistically significant difference ($P<0.05$). The mean axial lengths in Immersion A-scan group and Contact A-scan group were 23.07 and 22.65 with statistically significant difference ($P<0.05$). The mean IOL powers in Immersion A-scan group and Contact A-scan group were 20.37 and 21.21 with statistically significant difference ($P<0.05$). (Table 2) In the present study, the majority of patients in Immersion A-scan group had BCVA >6/12 (98%) compared to Contact A-scan group (84%) with statistically significant difference ($P<0.05$). (Table 3) Ademola-Popoola DS et al. [8] in a study observed the immersion technique gave longer axial length measurement compared to the contact method similar to present study. Corneal compression causes a decrease in anterior chamber depth and axis readings, which explains the shorter biometric values obtained using the contact approach.[9]

Since, determining the IOL power that would produce the desired post-operative refraction is the

most prevalent indication for ocular biometry, this could have an impact on the choice of IOL power. Therefore, a refractive error of roughly 0–3 dioptres could be the clinically significant difference for an eye of typical length. This is comparable to other reports of 0.26 mm (SD 0.3) by Kronbauer et al.[10] and 0.24 mm by Shammas.[11] Other authors reported similar significant differences between the two methods in measuring ocular biometry, particularly axial length measurement. They demonstrated that the contact method resulted in an unsystematic difference between the two methods of approximately 18% greater intra-ocular lens calculation errors, with a difference of up to 0.47 mm among various examiners.[12-14]

The higher accuracy was ascribed to the absence of ocular compression and the immersion technique's increased sensitivity to probe displacement.[15] This discrepancy is thought to be caused by the pressure the ultrasonic probe applies to the eye, which causes corneal indentation and axial length shortening. In contrast, the immersion technique involves inserting the ultrasonic probe into a shell that contains a coupling fluid to prevent direct contact with the cornea and, consequently, compression.[16]

However, in their study of 36 eyes, Henessy et al.[17] discovered that the contact method yielded a longer axial length measurement of 0.03 mm. They also proposed that repeating measurements made contact ultrasound biometry comparable to immersion, with no discernible difference in mean axial length measurements.

The study's scope is restricted to a small number of ALs. As a result, applying the current study's findings to eyes that are very long or very short is challenging. Furthermore, no predictions can be made for eyes with atypical K or a skewed anterior to posterior segment ratio because the current study solely comprised simple cataract procedures.

Conclusion

The present study concludes that the immersion technique had better repeatability, compared to Contact A-scan for intra-ocular lens power calculation. Thus, it is ideal in a training hospital setting with limited resources.

References

1. Norrby S. Sources of error in intraocular lens power calculation. J Cataract Refract Surg.

- 2008; 34:368–376.
2. Hrebцова J., Skorkovska S., Vasku A. Comparison of contact and immersion techniques of ultrasound biometry in terms of target postoperative refraction. *Cesk Slov Oftalmol.* 2009; 65:143–146.
 3. Holzer MP, Mamusa M, Auffarth GU. Accuracy of a new partial coherence interferometry analyser for biometric measurements. *Br J Ophthalmol* 2009; 93:807–810.
 4. R J., F M. The contact and immersion ultrasound methods compared using the ray tracing method. *Optica Applicata.* 2010; XL: 77–92.
 5. Hoffmann P.C., Hutz W.W., Eckhardt H.B., Heuring A.H. Intraocular lens calculation and ultrasound biometry: immersion and contact procedures. *Klin Monbl Augenheilkd.* 1998; 213:161–165.
 6. Olsen T. Calculation of intraocular lens power: a review. *Acta Ophthalmol Scand.* 2007; 85:472–485.
 7. Packer M., Fine I.H., Hoffman R.S., Coffman P.G., Brown L.K. Immersion A-scan compared with partial coherence interferometry: outcomes analysis. *J Cataract Refract Surg.* 2002; 28:239–242.
 8. Ademola-Popoola DS, Nzeh DA, Saka SE, Olokoba LB, Obajolowo TS. Comparison of ocular biometry measurements by applanation and immersion A-scan techniques. *J Curr Ophthalmol.* 2016 Feb 9; 27(3-4):110-4.
 9. Abu El Einen K.G., Shalaby M.H., El Shiwiy H.T. Immersion B-guided versus contact A-mode biometry for accurate measurement of axial length and intraocular lenspower calculation in siliconized eyes. *Retina.* 2011; 31:262–265.
 10. Kronbauer A.L., Kronbauer F.L., Kronbauer C.L. Comparative study of the biometric measurements made by immersion and contact techniques. *Arq Bras Oftalmol.* 2006; 69:875–880.
 11. Shammas H.J. A comparison of immersion and contact techniques for axial length measurement. *J Am Intraocul Implant Soc.* 1984; 10:444–447.
 12. Ben-Zion I., Neely D.E., Plager D.A., Ofner S., Sprunger D.T., Roberts G.J. Accuracy of IOL calculations in children: a comparison of immersion versus contact A-scanbiometry. *J AAPOS.* 2008; 12:440–444.
 13. Hitzenberger C.K., Drexler W., Dolezal C. Measurement of the axial length of cataract eyes by laser Doppler interferometry. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci.* 1993; 34:1886–1893.
 14. Olsen T., Nielsen P.J. Immersion versus contact technique in the measurement of axial length by ultrasound. *Acta Ophthalmol (Copenh)* 1989; 67:101–102.
 15. Falhar Martin R.J. The contact and immersin ultrasound methods compared using the ray tracing method. *Optica Applicata.* 2010; XL: 77–92.
 16. Attah H. *Ophthalmic ultrasound, a practical guide.* 2008. pp. 555–560.
 17. Hennessy M.P., Franzco, Chan D.G. Contact versus immersion biometry of axial length before cataract surgery. *J Cataract Refract Surg.* 2003; 29:2195–2198.